

1 **Development of auxin reporters in oilseed rape (*Brassica napus*)**

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20 Running title: Auxin reporters in *Brassica napus*

21

22 **Abstract**

23 Auxin is a key phytohormone that regulates all aspects of plant growth, development, and
24 environmental responses, making the precise analysis of its distribution and signaling essential
25 for understanding plant adaptation and physiological processes. However, despite the
26 agricultural importance of oilseed rape (*Brassica napus*), the lack of robust, species-specific
27 molecular tools limits detailed studies of hormone signaling in this crop. Here, we developed
28 and characterized reporter systems for the sensitive visualization and quantification of auxin
29 distribution and signaling in *B. napus*. The DR5cc auxin signaling reporter and a novel synthetic
30 auxin-responsive reporter, BIP3, assembled from promoter fragments of three oilseed rape *IAA*
31 genes, were generated to drive GUS expression. In hairy roots, both reporters showed auxin-
32 responsive expression in the root apical meristem that became broader after auxin treatment. In
33 transgenic seedlings, flowers at anthesis, and 12-day-old embryos, DR5cc exhibited a more
34 defined expression pattern than BIP3. To monitor real-time auxin dynamics under abiotic stress,

35 DR5cc fluorescent reporters were employed in hairy roots. Mannitol and NaCl treatments
36 induced a time-dependent increase in fluorescence, peaking at 6–12 h before returning to basal
37 levels after 24 h. Furthermore, dual-reporter assays enabled simultaneous monitoring of auxin
38 and cytokinin signaling, revealing distinct hormone-specific spatial responses in hairy roots.
39 Finally, we established a quantitative DII (qDII) reporter system using degron domains from *B.*
40 *napus* Aux/IAA proteins, providing a high-resolution quantitative readout of auxin depletion.
41 Together, these reporter systems enable spatial, temporal, and quantitative analyses of auxin
42 dynamics during development and stress adaptation in oilseed rape.

43

44 **Introduction**

45 Plant hormones, or phytohormones, are a diverse group of naturally occurring organic
46 compounds that play crucial roles in regulating plant growth, development, and responses to
47 environmental stimuli. These signaling molecules function at low concentrations and often
48 interact in complex networks to coordinate physiological processes. Insights into hormone
49 interactions and signaling pathways deepen our understanding of plant biology and enhance
50 strategies for crop improvement. Auxin, one of the key phytohormones, regulates numerous
51 developmental processes, including embryogenesis, tropic responses, apical dominance, and
52 cell division, elongation, and differentiation^{1–3}. Indole-3-acetic acid (IAA) is the predominant
53 natural auxin, though several other endogenous (e.g., indole-3-butyric acid [IBA], phenylacetic
54 acid) and synthetic auxin analogs (e.g., 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid [2,4-D], 1-
55 naphthaleneacetic acid [NAA]) also functionally mimic auxin activity⁴. Auxin signaling is
56 primarily mediated by a pathway that involves TRANSPORT INHIBITOR RESPONSE
57 1/AUXIN SIGNALING F-BOX (TIR1/AFB) receptor proteins, AUXIN RESPONSE FACTOR
58 (ARF) transcription factors, and Aux/IAA repressor proteins. In the absence of auxin, Aux/IAA
59 proteins inhibit ARF activity. Auxin binding to TIR1 enhances its affinity for Aux/IAs,
60 promoting their ubiquitination and proteasomal degradation, thereby releasing ARFs to activate
61 target gene expression⁵. TIR/AFB receptors exhibit adenylate cyclase activity, catalyzing the
62 local production of the second messenger cAMP, which may contribute to transcriptional
63 regulation^{6,7}.

64 Auxin distribution can be visualized directly using immunolocalization, labeled auxins, or
65 biosensors. However, indirect monitoring through transcriptional reporters remains the most
66 widely used approach due to its simplicity and accessibility⁸. These systems employ natural or
67 synthetic promoters containing auxin-response elements (AuxREs) to drive reporter gene
68 expression, which depends on the presence of auxin signaling components (e.g., receptors,
69 ARFs). As such, these reporters reflect auxin-responsive transcriptional activity rather than
70 auxin concentration *per se*.

71 Ulmasov et al. (1995)⁹ showed that AuxREs typically contain the core hexamer 5'-TGTCTC-
72 3', which mediates transcriptional responses to auxin. Building on this sequence, the DR5
73 reporter was created as a synthetic promoter composed of multiple tandem repeats of an 11-bp
74 sequence (5'-CCTTTTGTCTC-3') fused to a minimal CaMV 35S promoter¹⁰. To enhance
75 signal strength and spatial coverage, the DR5rev variant was developed by arranging nine

76 AuxRE repeats in reverse orientation¹¹. Subsequent structural studies revealed that ARF1 and
77 ARF5 proteins preferentially bind a related motif, 5'-TGTCGG-3'¹². Incorporating this higher-
78 affinity sequence, DR5v2 replaced the TGTCTC repeats with TGTCGG, yielding a promoter
79 with greater ARF binding and improved sensitivity to auxin¹³.

80 In plant promoters, AuxREs can occur as pairs of TGTCNN motifs arranged as direct, inverted,
81 or everted repeats, with varying spacing between the sites. In *Arabidopsis*, the direct repeat with
82 a five-base-pair spacer is most strongly associated with auxin-responsive gene activation,
83 highlighting its role as a highly effective regulatory architecture for auxin-dependent
84 transcription¹⁴. AuxRE variants (TGTCNN) were screened across angiosperms, with
85 TGTCCC, TGTCGG, TGTCGA, and TGTCTC identified as the most highly conserved¹⁵.
86 Gene ontology analysis linked regulatory regions containing the TGTCGG motif to cell wall
87 biosynthesis genes and those with the TGTCCC motif to auxin-responsive genes. To test
88 functional relevance, DR5 promoters incorporating individual variants (TGTCCC, TGTCTC,
89 TGTCAC, or the nonconserved TGTCGC) were engineered and reporter activity was assessed
90 in *Arabidopsis*. All constructs showed dose-dependent auxin responsiveness, but the response
91 strength varied markedly, being highest for TGTCCC¹⁵.

92 In addition to synthetic promoters, promoter fragments from auxin-responsive genes have also
93 been employed as auxin reporters. Examples include promoter regions of *GRETCHEN HAGEN*
94 *3 (GH3)* and *SMALL AUXIN-UP RNA 10A (SAUR10A)*, which have been used to drive the
95 expression of β -glucuronidase (GUS) or fluorescent proteins^{16–18}. The pIAA motif synthetic
96 auxin reporter was designed with native TGTCCC-containing promoter fragments from
97 *Arabidopsis IAA1/IAA2* and *Populus trichocarpa IAA1* positioned upstream of a minimal
98 CaMV 35S promoter. Its expression pattern was tested in *Arabidopsis* and tomato, revealing an
99 overlapping yet broader expression domain compared with the classical DR5 reporter in both
100 roots and shoots¹⁵.

101 Distinct from promoter-based reporters, degron-based systems provide a direct and rapid means
102 of monitoring auxin input by exploiting the auxin-dependent degradation of domain II (DII) in
103 Aux/IAA proteins. In the DII-VENUS system, the DII of IAA28, containing a degron motif
104 required for auxin-induced degradation, is fused to the fast-maturing yellow fluorescent protein
105 VENUS. Auxin triggers TIR1/AFB-mediated ubiquitin–proteasome degradation of the fusion,
106 producing a fluorescence signal inversely correlated with cellular auxin levels^{19,20}. A mutated,
107 auxin-insensitive mDII variant was designed to serve as a stable control. The ratiometric R2D2
108 system further improves quantification by co-expressing DII-VENUS and mDII-tdTomato,
109 each driven by its own RPS5A promoter within a single construct¹³. The quantitative DII-
110 VENUS (qDII) variant was developed to measure auxin distribution in the *Arabidopsis* shoot
111 apical meristem²¹. In this system, a single RPS5A promoter drives the expression of both the
112 auxin-sensitive DII-VENUS and TagBFP, a stable blue fluorescent protein used as a reference
113 for normalization, with the two proteins separated by a 2A peptide.

114 The degron motif (VGWPP[V/I][R/G]XXR) of the DII domain interacts with TIR1/AFB
115 receptor in an auxin-dependent manner. Variations in the degron sequence directly affect
116 Aux/IAA stability and auxin sensitivity. Regions flanking the degron, including the degron tail

117 and proximal motifs such as the Lys-Arg (KR) dipeptide, further modulate auxin-dependent
118 degradation dynamics ^{22–26}.

119 In this study, we established a reporter system that may serve as a sensitive and robust tool for
120 visualization and quantification of auxin levels and response distribution in oilseed rape, a
121 globally important oilseed crop.

122

123 **Results**

124 **A DR5cc auxin reporter for oilseed rape**

125 Building on the previously designed synthetic DR5 promoter ¹⁰, we developed a variant of this
126 reporter for oilseed rape. In place of the original core AuxRE motif TGTCTC, we introduced
127 the TGTCCC motif, which has been shown to confer high auxin responsiveness in *Arabidopsis*
128 ¹⁵, and designated the construct as DR5cc. As in the original DR5 construct, nine repeats of the
129 core motif are separated by 5-bp spacers. To reduce repetitive sequence composition, however,
130 we supplemented the previously used CCTTT spacer ^{10,15} with additional 5-bp sequences
131 naturally occurring in *Aux/IAA* promoters of oilseed rape and *Arabidopsis*. For example, the
132 ATCTT sequence, found between two core motifs in the *BnaIAA1* promoter, was incorporated
133 between the first two TGTCCC motifs in DR5cc (Figure 1A). The DR5cc sequence was fused
134 to the minimal CaMV 35S promoter to drive expression of β -glucuronidase (GUS). Two
135 constructs were generated, differing in the presence or absence of the 5'-untranslated region (5'-
136 UTR) of tobacco mosaic virus (TMV) RNA (Ω), and designated as DR5cc-GUS and DR5cc-
137 Ω -GUS. In addition, we included a negative control containing only the minimal CaMV 35S
138 promoter and a positive control in which GUS expression was driven by the full CaMV 35S
139 promoter (Figure 1).

140 *B. napus* DH12075 was transformed using C58C1 *Agrobacterium* strain harboring *pRiA4*
141 plasmid and one of the binary vectors. Independent hairy root lines were subsequently screened
142 for GUS activity. In the hairy root lines under study, the transgene copy number was determined
143 using quantitative PCR (qPCR). Following previous studies ^{27,28}, the *acetyl-CoA carboxylase*
144 (*ACC*) gene was selected as an endogenous control. Primers and a probe for qPCR were
145 designed to selectively amplify the A-subgenome copy (*ACC-A*). The transgene (*uidA* gene
146 commonly referred to as the GUS gene) copy number in hairy roots was then determined
147 following the approach described by Weng et al. (2024) 29.

148 Hairy root lines carrying the DR5cc-GUS and DR5cc- Ω -GUS constructs exhibited similar
149 pattern of auxin signaling (Figure 1B). In the absence of exogenous auxin, GUS activity was
150 detected in the root apical meristem (RAM). Following auxin treatment (0.1 μ M and 1 μ M
151 NAA for 12 h), the GUS signal became widely distributed. As expected, hairy roots carrying
152 the minimal CaMV 35S promoter did not show any GUS activity either before or after auxin
153 treatment, whereas the positive controls containing the full CaMV 35S promoter exhibited
154 strong signal throughout the root (Supplementary Figure S1).

155 In addition, *B. napus* DH12075 was transformed using the K599 *Agrobacterium* strain
 156 harboring the DR5cc- Ω -GUS construct (Figure 1C). The transformation efficiency using the
 157 injection-based method was $92.6 \pm 2.6\%$, which was similar to that obtained with the C58C1
 158 strain ($96.7 \pm 2.9\%$)³⁰. The difference between the hairy root lines transformed with K599 and
 159 those transformed with C58C1 became evident during growth in tissue culture. Whereas the
 160 C58C1 lines exhibited vigorous growth, the K599 lines developed slowly, with some lines
 161 performing very poorly or dying on the plates (Supplementary Figure S2).

162 No major differences in GUS localization were observed between DR5cc- Ω -GUS lines
 163 generated with the C58C1 and K599 strains. However, the transgene copy number appears to
 164 influence the intensity and diffusion of the GUS expression pattern in lines produced by both
 165 *Agrobacterium* strains, with lines containing multiple GUS copies showing stronger GUS
 166 intensity than those with fewer transgene copies (Figure 1B and 1C).

167

168 Figure 1: DR5cc reporter in oilseed rape. (A) Schematic representation of DR5cc constructs
 169 transformed into *Brassica napus* DH12075. (B) Hairy root lines induced by the *Agrobacterium*
 170 strain C58C1 carrying DR5cc-GUS and DR5cc- Ω -GUS constructs, illustrating endogenous
 171 auxin signaling (without induction) and responses following induction by exogenous auxin
 172 treatment (NAA at 0.1 μ M and 1 μ M for 12 h). For the DR5cc- Ω -GUS constructs, both low-
 173 copy (1 copy) and high-copy (9 copies) lines are shown. For the DR5cc-GUS construct, a line
 174 containing 3 copies is presented. Scale bars represent 500 μ m. (C) Hairy root lines induced by
 175 the *Agrobacterium* strain K599 carrying the DR5cc- Ω -GUS construct, analyzed under non-
 176 induced conditions and after induction with 0.1 μ M NAA. The low-copy line contains 1 copy,
 177 whereas the high-copy line contains 6 copies of the transgene. Scale bars represent 200 μ m.

178

179 A new synthetic auxin reporter specific for oilseed rape

180 To better mimic the context of a native promoter, we designed an auxin reporter comprising
181 three fragments, each 51 – 52 bp long, derived from *B. napus* promoters *BnaIAA1*, *BnaIAA2*,
182 and *BnaIAA4*. Each fragment contains the native TGTCCC AuxRE motif (Figure 2A). As
183 oilseed rape is an allotetraploid species, it contains multiple copies of each gene derived from
184 the A and C subgenomes. The copies chosen for the design of the reporter were identified based
185 on the presence of TGTCCC motifs in their sequences (Supplementary Figure S3) and
186 supporting expression data ³¹. Interestingly, the *BnaIAA4* promoter contains a third TGTCCC
187 motif arranged as an inverted repeat downstream of the second TGTCCC motif, separated by 9
188 bp (Figure 2A). The construct was designated as BIP3 (*Brassica IAA* promoter – 3x). The
189 synthetic promoter was fused to a minimal CaMV 35S promoter driving GUS expression, and
190 two variants were generated, including the Ω 5' UTR (BIP3- Ω -GUS) or not (BIP3-GUS).

191 In the BIP3 reporter lines, endogenous auxin activity was weak in the RAM. Application of 0.1
192 μ M and 1 μ M NAA for 12 h broadened the GUS signal, showing a clear concentration-
193 dependent gradient, with the 1 μ M treatment producing a stronger and more extensive response
194 (Figure 2B). The presence of the UTR was associated with a modest enhancement of GUS
195 expression in BIP3 lines.

196

197 Figure 2. BIP3 reporter in oilseed rape. (A) Schematic representation of the BIP3 auxin reporter
198 composed of fragments derived from three *BnaIAA* promoters containing AuxREs as either
199 direct or inverted repeat. (B) Detection of auxin signalling in hairy roots transformed with
200 *Agrobacterium* C58C1 carrying the BIP3-GUS or BIP3- Ω -GUS constructs following induction
201 with 0.1 μ M or 1 μ M NAA for 12 h, or in the absence of induction (Mock). Both lines contain
202 3 copies of the transgene. Scale bars represent 500 μ m.

203

204 **Auxin signaling in regenerated plants**

205 Following analysis in hairy roots, we regenerated selected hairy root lines carrying the DR5cc-
206 GUS, DR5cc- Ω -GUS, BIP3-GUS, and BIP3- Ω -GUS constructs. The T0 regenerants derived
207 from transformation with the C58C1 strain exhibited the typical *Ri* phenotype, often
208 characterized by a dwarfed stature and curly leaves^{30,32}. These T0 regenerants were
209 backcrossed to the DH12075 wild type (WT). The resulting backcrossed T1 plants were
210 genotyped for the presence of T-DNAs derived from the binary vector (GUS transgene) and
211 from the *Ri* plasmid. In the C58C1 strain, the *Ri* T-DNA is divided into two separate regions,
212 the left (TL) and the right (TR), which were analyzed independently. Of the 244 plants screened,
213 derived from six independent transgenic lines carrying either the DR5cc or BIP3 constructs, the
214 majority (79.5%) contained all three T-DNAs (+GUS, +TL, +TR). No T-DNA was detected in
215 10.7% of the plants (-GUS, -TL, -TR), while 9.8% lacked the TR region (+GUS, +TL, -TR).
216 Notably, none of the analyzed plants exhibited a genotype containing the GUS transgene while
217 lacking both *Ri* T-DNA regions (+GUS, -TL, -TR).

218 The expression pattern of the auxin signaling-based reporters was examined across different
219 tissues in T1 plants, including 4-day-old seedlings, root tips, flowers at anthesis, and 12-day-
220 old embryos (Figure 3). As expected, the positive control harboring the full CaMV 35S
221 promoter showed ubiquitous GUS expression, whereas no signal was detected in the WT plants
222 (Figure 3A).

223 DR5cc-GUS reporters exhibited restricted expression in root tips, confined to the quiescent
224 centre (QC) and columella cells (Figure 3B). In flowers, the signal was detected in the anther
225 connective tissue, while in seeds, it was localized to the embryonic root pole. In contrast,
226 DR5cc- Ω -GUS plants displayed broader and more stable expression. In seedlings, staining
227 extended beyond the root apex to vasculature, lateral root primordia, and the root-hypocotyl
228 junction. In flowers, signal was detected in sepal vasculature and within the anther connective
229 tissue. In seeds, embryos showed widespread strong staining throughout the cotyledons and
230 root.

231 BIP3-GUS exhibited weak, diffuse staining, with low signal in the root tip, weak staining at the
232 hypocotyl-root junction, faint signal in anther connective tissue, and no detectable staining in
233 embryos (Figure 3C). Addition of the 5' UTR in BIP3- Ω -GUS enhanced reporter sensitivity,
234 resulting in more defined staining in columella, stronger signal in vasculature near the root-
235 hypocotyl junction, and expression in pedicel, anther filaments, connective tissue, and anther
236 lobe. In embryos, broad staining was observed, resembling that of a strong auxin reporter. GUS
237 staining patterns were consistent across independent lines harboring the same construct
238 (Supplementary Figure S4).

239 Reporter functionality in transgenic plants was further confirmed by local application of 50 μ M
240 NAA to inflorescences of the examined lines, which resulted in broader staining after 24 h
241 compared with mock-treated controls (Supplementary Figure S5).

242

243 Figure 3. Histochemical GUS staining of different tissues of *B. napus* transgenic plants. (A)
244 positive and negative controls. (B) DR5cc-GUS (+/- Ω). (C) BIP3-GUS (+/- Ω). Scale bars
245 represent 2 mm (seedlings, flowers), 200 μm (root tips), and 500 μm (embryos). Arrowheads
246 indicate the quiescent centre and columella cells in the root tip, the anther connective tissue in
247 the flower, and the embryonic root pole in the embryo for DR5cc-GUS; the sepal vasculature
248 in the flower for DR5cc-Ω-GUS; and the anther filament in the flower for BIP3-Ω-GUS.

249

250 Abiotic stress-induced auxin signaling response in oilseed rape

251 To enable live imaging of auxin responses, we generated fluorescent reporters by fusing the
252 DR5cc-Ω to sequences encoding the VENUS and mCherry proteins, and transformed the

253 constructs into *B. napus* DH12075 using the C58C1 strain. In four tested independent hairy root
254 lines, application of 1 μ M NAA elicited a measurable auxin signaling response after 6 and 24
255 h, as evidenced by significant increase in fluorescence. The response exhibited a broad spatial
256 distribution and was more pronounced in the VENUS fusions (Supplementary Figure S6).

257 Auxin plays a key role in integrating abiotic stress signals and mediating plant responses³³. To
258 investigate auxin output in *B. napus* under stress conditions, hairy roots expressing DR5cc- Ω -
259 VENUS and DR5cc- Ω -mCherry were treated with 150 mM mannitol or 75 mM NaCl to mimic
260 drought and salinity, respectively. Fluorescence intensity was quantified at 1, 6, 12, and 24 h to
261 monitor temporal dynamics. Both treatments induced a transient auxin response in the root apex
262 (Figure 4, Supplementary Figure S7). No significant changes relative to mock-treated controls
263 were observed after 1 h of application of the stress inducers, whereas fluorescence intensity
264 increased significantly at 6 and 12 h and returned to control levels after 24 h of treatment. Such
265 temporal dynamic pattern was reproducible across independent transgenic lines and reporter
266 variants (Figure 4, Supplementary Figure S7 – S9).

268 Figure 4. Stress-induced auxin signaling dynamics in *B. napus* hairy roots. **(A)** Maximum
269 intensity projections of root tips expressing DR5cc- Ω -VENUS under mock and abiotic stress
270 conditions (150 mM mannitol or 75 mM NaCl), imaged at 1, 6, 12, and 24 h of treatment. Scale
271 bars represent 40 μ m. **(B, C)** Quantification of relative VENUS **(B)** and mCherry **(C)**
272 fluorescence intensities in mock- and stress-treated hairy roots at indicated time points. Error
273 bars indicate SD (n = individual roots); *P < 0.05; ***P < 0.001; Dunnett's test. For each time
274 point, values are normalized to mock. Images corresponding to **(C)** are presented in
275 Supplementary Figure S7.

276

277 **Concurrent analysis of cytokinin and auxin signaling in tissue culture**

278 We previously demonstrated the responsiveness of the *Arabidopsis thaliana*-derived TCSv2
279 reporter to application of cytokinin and abiotic stress in hairy roots of *B. napus* cv. Darmor and
280 *B. rapa* R-o-18³⁴. In this study, we introduced the same construct, TCSv2-VENUS, into *B.*
281 *napus* DH12075 and regenerated plants from the transformed hairy roots. The cytokinin
282 TCSv2-VENUS reporter was functional in the roots of regenerated plants, as evidenced by its
283 induction following a 2 h treatment with 5 μ M BAP (Figure 5A, B).

284 The TCSv2-VENUS plants were subsequently transformed using the *Agrobacterium* strain
285 C58C1 carrying the DR5cc- Ω -mCherry auxin reporter construct. Two independent hairy root
286 lines were treated with NAA (1 μ M, 24 h) and / or BAP (5 μ M, 2 h), and mCherry and VENUS
287 fluorescence intensities were quantified in root tips (Figure 5C, D, Supplementary Figure S10).
288 In both lines, only the reporter corresponding to the applied hormone (VENUS for BAP and
289 mCherry for NAA) showed significant increase in fluorescence and broader signal distribution,
290 demonstrating that both hormonal responses can be simultaneously monitored in *B. napus* hairy
291 roots.

292

293 Figure 5. Cytokinin and auxin reporter activity in *B. napus*. (A) Maximum intensity projections
 294 of mock- and BAP-treated (5 μ M, 2 h) roots from regenerated plants expressing TCSv2-
 295 VENUS. Scale bars represent 50 μ m. (B) Quantification of relative VENUS fluorescence
 296 intensity in mock- and BAP-treated root tips. Error bars indicate SD (n = individual roots); ***P
 297 < 0.001; Welch's t-test. Values are normalized to mock. (C) Maximum intensity projections of
 298 hairy roots co-expressing TCSv2-VENUS and DR5cc- Ω -mCherry treated with mock, NAA (1
 299 μ M, 24 h), and / or BAP (5 μ M, 2 h). Images are shown as VENUS (top row), mCherry (middle
 300 row) and merged channels (bottom row: magenta color for DR5cc- Ω -mCherry and yellow for
 301 TCSv2-VENUS). Scale bars represent 20 μ m. (D) Quantification of relative VENUS (left) and

302 mCherry (right) fluorescence intensities in mock- and hormone-treated hairy roots. Error bars
303 indicate SD (n = individual roots); ***P < 0.001; Dunnett's test. For each channel, values are
304 normalized to mock.

305

306 **DII-based reporters for oilseed rape**

307 We developed a degron-based quantitative DII (qDII) reporter system for oilseed rape. The DII
308 domains of two *B. napus* Aux/IAA proteins (IAA2 and IAA17) were synthesized in frame with
309 the VENUS fluorescent protein. Each construct also includes TagBFP, a stable blue fluorescent
310 protein that is not degraded and serves as a reference for signal normalization. The two
311 fluorescent proteins are separated by a 2A peptide, and the expression of the constructs is driven
312 by the full CaMV 35S promoter. The DII domains contain not only the degron motif
313 (VGWPPVRS[Y/S]R) but also the upstream region with the KR motif and the downstream
314 degron tail (Figure 6A), as these elements have been shown to be important for auxin-dependent
315 degradation²³. Considering the A and C subgenomes and multiple gene homologs, the *B. napus*
316 sequences encoding the DII domains were selected based on the presence of characteristic
317 motifs (Supplementary Figure S11) and supporting expression data³¹.

318 Hairy roots carrying the IAA2-qDII or IAA17-qDII constructs were treated with 10 μ M NAA
319 for 2 h and imaged in epidermal cells within the root transition zone, revealing a significant
320 decrease in the nuclear VENUS/TagBFP ratio in all tested lines (Figure 6; Supplementary
321 Figure S12). In contrast, nuclear TagBFP fluorescence remained stable upon NAA treatment,
322 confirming the stability of the reference channel (Supplementary Figure S13). These results
323 demonstrate that the qDII system is functional and enables quantitative readout of auxin
324 responses in *B. napus* hairy roots.

325

326 Figure 6. qDII reporters are auxin responsive in *B. napus* hairy roots. (A) Schematic
327 representation of the selected DII domains. (B, C) IAA2-qDII and (D, E) IAA17-qDII showing
328 representative epidermal cell images under mock and NAA (10 μ M, 2 h) conditions, with
329 TagBFP (left) and VENUS (right) channels (B, D), and corresponding VENUS/TagBFP
330 fluorescence intensity quantifications (C, E). Values are normalized to mock. Error bars indicate
331 SD (n = individual roots); ***P < 0.001; Welch's t-test. Scale bars represent 20 μ m.

332

333 Discussion

334 *Agrobacterium* strains carrying hairy root-inducing (Ri) plasmids trigger abnormal root
335 formation in host plants by transferring T-DNA into the plant genome at wound sites.
336 Expression of T-DNA genes, particularly the *rol* loci, drives hairy root development ³².
337 *Agrobacterium* strains harboring both an Ri plasmid and an engineered binary vector are widely
338 employed for the delivery of foreign DNA into plant cells. Hairy root tissue culture expressing
339 DR5 transgene has previously been demonstrated to be a suitable system for monitoring auxin
340 signaling across various species ³⁵⁻³⁷. In our study, we developed auxin reporters specifically

341 for *Brassica* species by using sequences derived from oilseed rape and we demonstrated their
342 functionality and auxin responsiveness in both hairy root cultures and regenerated plants.

343 In hairy root cultures generated by two different *Agrobacterium* strains (the cucumopine-type
344 strain K599 and the transconjugant C58C1 carrying the agropine-type *pRiA4*), auxin signaling
345 remained comparable. Differences were observed only in the growth of the hairy root lines,
346 with those derived from K599 exhibiting slower growth than those obtained after
347 transformation with C58C1. This observation is consistent with a previous study indicating that
348 T-DNA-encoded genes acquired from the K599 strain negatively affect root growth under both
349 normal and stress conditions in tobacco regenerants ³⁸.

350 In regenerated plants, attempts to segregate the Ri plasmid T-DNA from the T-DNA of the
351 binary vector were unsuccessful. A similar limitation was observed in additional reporter lines
352 developed in our laboratory (data not shown). One possible explanation is the use of the
353 transconjugant C58C1 strain, which may exhibit an increased propensity for co-integration of
354 multiple T-DNAs (specifically those derived from the *Ri* plasmid and the binary vector) into
355 the same genomic locus. Previous studies using *A. tumefaciens* have investigated co-
356 transformation frequencies of two T-DNAs. With the C58C1 strain, the described co-
357 transformation system favored genetically linked integration of the two T-DNAs ³⁹, whereas a
358 study employing the LBA4404 strain did not observe preferential integration into linked loci
359 ⁴⁰. As our optimized protocol utilized the transconjugant C58C1 strain carrying *pRiA4*, this
360 phenomenon may be associated with the *Agrobacterium* strain used. Alternatively, T-DNA
361 integration patterns are known to be influenced by other factors, including plant species, the
362 cell type targeted for transformation, vector design, and the transformation method employed
363 ^{41,42}. In our case, the injection-based transformation method may also contribute to this effect.

364 Despite the confirmed presence of Ri plasmid T-DNA in regenerated oilseed rape plants
365 exhibiting the Ri phenotype, auxin signaling in these lines was comparable to that observed in
366 *Arabidopsis* plants lacking *Ri* T-DNA ^{43,44}. Thus, although genes located on the Ri plasmid T-
367 DNA can modulate auxin homeostasis and enhance plant sensitivity to this hormone ^{45,46},
368 oilseed rape regenerants remain suitable for auxin signaling studies.

369 Reporter systems enable real-time monitoring of phytohormone signaling responses during
370 plant development. Although well established in *Arabidopsis* ⁴⁷, they are increasingly applied
371 in other species, including maize ⁴⁸, rice ⁴⁹, and tomato ⁵⁰. Previously, we demonstrated stress-
372 induced changes in cytokinin signaling using a TCS-based reporter in *Brassica* hairy roots ³⁴.
373 Here, we extend this approach to auxin by analyzing *B. napus* hairy roots expressing DR5
374 fluorescent reporters. We observed a transient increase in DR5 signal in root tips exposed to
375 osmotic and salt stress, suggesting a temporary change in auxin responsiveness. In *Arabidopsis*,
376 osmotic and salt stress alter local auxin maxima in roots within hours ⁴³. Similarly, salinity
377 induces rapid redistribution of auxin signaling output in root tips during halotropic growth ⁵¹.
378 These observations are consistent with the dynamic nature of auxin distribution in plant tissues
379 and its role in adaptive growth responses ^{33,52}. Our results further support the use of DR5-based
380 reporters and demonstrate their applicability for monitoring early stress responses in crop
381 species.

382 DR5 reporters reflect downstream signaling output rather than auxin levels themselves. To more
383 directly assess cellular auxin distribution, reporters based on the auxin-sensitive domain (DII)
384 have been developed as auxin input reporters⁸. Previous studies have shown that regions
385 flanking the degron modulate degradation dynamics^{23,25}. Therefore, we developed a qDII
386 reporter incorporating the degron together with key flanking regions, including the degron tail
387 and proximal KR motif, derived from two Aux/IAA proteins, IAA2 and IAA17. Using a hairy
388 root transformation system, we demonstrated the functionality of the qDII reporter in oilseed
389 rape.

390 In conclusion, we developed auxin input and output reporters for oilseed rape, enabling
391 visualization of auxin signaling in both hairy root systems and whole plants. These reporters
392 provide a versatile platform for the rapid evaluation of auxin dynamics in transformed roots and
393 for monitoring spatial auxin patterns *in planta*, expanding the toolkit for studying hormone
394 response in crop species.

395

396 **Material and methods**

397 **Plant material**

398 Seeds of *B. napus* cultivar DH12075 used for transformation experiments were surface-
399 sterilized with 20% bleach and cultivated *in vitro* on half-strength Murashige and Skoog (MS)
400 medium (Duchefa) supplemented with 8 g/L plant agar (Duchefa) and 5 g/L sucrose. Growth
401 conditions were set to 21°C with a 16-h photoperiod in a controlled environment chamber.
402 Plants grown in soil were cultivated in a greenhouse under similar temperature and light
403 regimes.

404

405 **Reporters construction**

406 For DR5cc reporter construction, a fragment containing nine tandem AuxRE motifs (TGTCCC)
407 separated by 5-bp spacers, as naturally occurring in the promoters of *IAA* genes in *B. napus* and
408 *A. thaliana*, was synthesized together with a minimal CaMV 35S promoter (Invitrogen). The
409 fragment was cloned into the Addgene plasmid pICH41233 or pICH41295⁵³ to generate
410 reporter constructs with and without the Ω UTR, respectively. The Addgene plasmids used for
411 L1 and final L2 assembly⁵⁴ of the GUS reporter and fluorescent variants are detailed in
412 Supplementary Figure S14. The final plasmids used for plant transformation also contained a
413 gene conferring kanamycin (GUS and Venus variants)⁵⁵ or hygromycin (mCherry variant)⁵⁶
414 resistance.

415 For BIP3 reporter construction, promoter fragments of *BnaIAA* genes were selected from
416 multiple homoeologous copies present in the genome. For *BnaIAA1* and *BnaIAA4*, the A- and
417 C-subgenome copies (*BnaA08g30190D* and *BnaC08g09640D* for *IAA1*, *BnaA09g16590D* and
418 *BnaCnng63870D* for *IAA2*) were identical within the selected region (Supplementary Figure
419 S3). For *IAA2*, six copies were identified in the *B. napus* genome⁵⁷. The copy selected for
420 reporter construction (*BnaA01g24190D*, identical to *BnaC01g31190D* in this region) was

421 chosen based on the presence of TGTCCC motifs (Supplementary Figure S3) and expression
422 data from the Brassica Expression Database ³¹. A composite fragment consisting of three 51–
423 52 bp promoter elements, together with a minimal CaMV 35S promoter, was synthesized
424 (Invitrogen). The vectors were constructed using the MoClo protocol, employing the Addgene
425 plasmids specified in Supplementary Figure S14.

426 The DII domains of *IAA2* and *IAA17* (*BnaA01g24190D* and *BnaA08g27770D*, respectively),
427 selected for qDII reporter construction (Supplementary Figure S11), were synthesized
428 (Eurofins) and cloned into the Addgene plasmid pAGM1276 ⁵³. The DII domain was cloned in
429 frame by MoClo with a synthesized Venus–NLS–P2A–TagBFP–NLS fragment (Eurofins). The
430 construct contained the promoter and 5'UTR of CaMV 35S, and the *Atug7* terminator
431 (Supplementary Figure S14) ⁵⁴. The final plasmids used for plant transformation contained a
432 gene conferring kanamycin resistance ⁵⁵.

433

434 **Plant transformation and regeneration**

435 Hairy root induction was performed using the Ti plasmid-less *Agrobacterium tumefaciens*
436 strain C58C1 carrying the hairy root-inducing plasmid pRiA4b ⁵⁸, and *A. rhizogenes* strain
437 K599. Reporter constructs were introduced into *Agrobacterium* by electroporation.
438 Transformation of *B. napus* hypocotyls was carried out using an injection-based method, as
439 described in Jedličková et al. (2023) ⁵⁹. Independent hairy root lines were cultured on solid MS
440 medium supplemented with Gamborg B5 vitamins (Duchefa) and 30 g/L sucrose. The medium
441 was further supplemented with cefotaxime (200 mg/L) to suppress bacterial growth and
442 kanamycin (20 mg/L) or hygromycin (15 mg/L) for selection of reporter constructs. Cultures
443 were maintained at 22°C in the dark. Regeneration of selected hairy root lines was performed
444 according to an optimized protocol using 5 mg/L 6-benzylaminopurine (BAP) and 8 mg/L 1-
445 naphthaleneacetic acid (NAA) at 21°C under a 16-h photoperiod ⁵⁹. The regenerated plants (T0)
446 were backcrossed with wild-type DH12075, and the resulting T1 progeny were screened by
447 PCR using DNA extracted from leaves via the conventional cetyltrimethylammonium bromide
448 (CTAB) method ⁶⁰, with specific primers targeting *GUS*, *rolA* and *aux1* genes (encoded by TL
449 and TR of *Ri* plasmid, respectively; Supplementary Table S1).

450

451 **Transgene copy number assessment**

452 A 0.6 kb fragment of the reference gene *ACC* was amplified from genomic DNA of DH12075.
453 Two distinct copies of the gene were obtained by cloning. Sequence alignment revealed 82%
454 similarity between the two copies (Supplementary Figure S15). One copy originated from the
455 A subgenome (99.51% similarity to *ACC* in *B. rapa*), whereas the other was derived from the
456 C subgenome (98.18% similarity to *ACC* in *B. oleracea*). The cloned fragments of the *ACC*-A
457 and *ACC*-C copies were subsequently used to optimize qPCR conditions to specifically amplify
458 the *ACC*-A copy. The qPCR program consisted of an initial step at 50 °C for 2 min, followed
459 by 90 °C for 3 min, and 40 cycles of 95 °C for 15 s, 60 °C for 10 s, and 72 °C for 18 s. Reactions
460 were performed in a total volume of 10 µL, containing 5 µL of 2× PrimeTime Gene Expression

461 Master Mix (IDT), 0.25 μ L each of forward and reverse primers (10 μ M), 0.06 μ L of the probe
462 (10 μ M), 2 μ L of diluted DNA, and 1.94 μ L of nuclease-free water. Amplification was carried
463 out using an Applied Biosystems QuantStudio 12K Flex system. Primers and probes are
464 specified in Supplementary Table S1. Standard curves for *ACC-A* and *uidA* were generated
465 using five successive dilutions of oilseed rape genomic hairy root DNA (625, 125, 25, 5, and 1
466 ng per reaction). The slope and intercept of these standard curves were used to calculate
467 transgene copy number in each hairy root line according to the formula described by Weng et
468 al. (2004) 29. Analyses were performed using three biological replicates, each comprising three
469 technical replicates.

470

471 **Histochemical GUS staining**

472 Samples from regenerated plants (4-day-old seedlings, flowers, 12-day-old dissected embryos)
473 were immersed in GUS staining solution (0.5 M sodium phosphate buffer; pH 7, 50 mM
474 potassium ferricyanide (III) [Sigma], 0.2% Triton X-100 [Serva], 20 mg/ml X-Gluc [Thermo
475 Fisher Scientific] in DMSO), incubated in vacuum for 15 min, and stained for 16 h at 37 °C.
476 After staining, samples were washed in phosphate buffer and submerged in 70 % ethanol to
477 remove chlorophyll. Embryos were cleared with chloralhydrate solution (8/3/1 w/v/v
478 chloralhydrate [Lach-Ner], H₂O, Glycerol [Penta]). Transgenic hairy roots grown on plates
479 were excised (1-cm segments), incubated in GUS staining solution for 2 h at 37 °C and directly
480 imaged.

481

482 **Hormonal and abiotic stress treatment**

483 Root tips of transformed *B. napus* hairy roots were collected 10 days after subculture and
484 immersed in liquid MS-B5 medium supplemented with the respective chemicals or an equal
485 volume of DMSO (mock treatment). To investigate DR5cc auxin sensitivity, 1 μ M NAA was
486 applied and images were acquired after 6 and 24 h. Cytokinin sensitivity was assessed by
487 treating samples with 5 μ M BAP for 2 h. For the combined treatment, root tips were first
488 exposed to 1 μ M NAA for 22h, followed by an additional 2 h treatment with 1 μ M NAA and 5
489 μ M BAP. To assess auxin distribution in hairy root tips expressing the qDII reporter, 10 μ M
490 NAA was applied for 2 h. For stress response analysis, hairy roots were immersed in MS-B5
491 medium containing 75 mM NaCl (Penta) for salinity treatment and 150 mM D-Mannitol
492 (Sigma) for osmotic stress. MS-B5 medium alone was used for the mock treatment. Samples
493 were incubated at constant temperature of 21°C for 1, 6, 12, and 24 h. To assess TCSv2
494 cytokinin sensitivity in regenerated roots, 4-old-day seedlings were immersed in MS media
495 containing 10 μ M BAP for 2 h. Root tips were then collected and fixed in 4% PFA (Merck) in
496 PBS-T (1X PBS with 0.05% Triton X100 [Serva] pH 7.4) for 1 h under vacuum conditions,
497 followed by three washes of 1 h each in PBS-T (pH 7.4). Samples were transferred to a fresh
498 ClearSee alpha solution (10% (w/v) xylitol [Sigma], 15% (w/v) sodium deoxycholate [TCI],
499 25% (w/v) urea [Merck], 100 mM sodium sulfite [Sigma] in water). Images were acquired after
500 5 days of clearing at room temperature.

501

502 **Microscopy**

503 Images of GUS-stained samples were acquired using Olympus SZX16 stereomicroscope and
504 Zeiss AxioScope.A1 ZEN histological microscope. Confocal images of hairy root tips were
505 taken using Zeiss LSM 880 confocal microscope equipped with 25x objective. Three laser lines
506 were used in the study: 405 nm for TagBFP (detection at 410-507 nm), 514 nm for VENUS
507 (detection at 519-586 nm), and 561 nm for mCherry (detection at 578-696 nm). Scans were
508 performed at 1x zoom and in 1094*1094 or 2048*2048 pixel resolution. Laser intensity,
509 detector gain, and pinhole size were kept constant within each replicate with pixel time around
510 1 μ s. Maximum intensity projections of confocal z-stacks were acquired at 5.5 μ m intervals;
511 the number of slices varied depending on root thickness. The original uncropped and
512 unprocessed images have been deposited in the Zenodo repository
513 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.21030825>).

514

515 **Measurements and statistical analysis**

516 Fluorescence intensity was quantified using mean gray value measurements from defined
517 regions of interest. Background fluorescence was measured for each image and subtracted
518 prior to further analysis. For ratiometric qDII analysis, fluorescence was quantified in nuclei
519 expressing both a stable TagBFP and a degradable VENUS reporter. Ratios between VENUS /
520 TagBFP were calculated in 15 nuclei per root and averaged. In all assays, resulting values were
521 normalized to the average signal of mock control, and data are presented as relative
522 fluorescence intensity. All measurements were performed using ImageJ software⁶¹. A total of
523 3 - 4 independent experiments were performed for each analysis. Depending on the assay, one-
524 way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's test or a Welch's t-test were performed to determine
525 differences in relative fluorescence intensities in the roots under mock and treated conditions.

526

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534

535 **Author contributions**

536 VJ and HSR conceived and designed research. VJ, VP, MŠt, MZ, and MSe conducted
537 experiments. VJ, VP, and MZ analyzed data. VJ, VP and HSR wrote the manuscript. All authors
538 read and approved the manuscript.

539

540 **Data availability**

541 All data supporting the findings of this study are available in the article, in its supplementary
542 information files, and in Zenodo repository (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.21030825>).

543

544 **Conflicts of interest statement**

545 The authors declare no competing interests.

546

547 **Supplementary material**

548 **Supplementary Figure S1.** Hairy roots expressing the GUS reporter gene under the control of
549 either the minimal CaMV 35S promoter or the full CaMV 35S promoter, in the absence or
550 presence of auxin induction (1 μ M NAA). Scale bars represent 500 μ m.

551

552 **Supplementary Figure S2.** Growth of hairy roots induced by the C58C1 or K599
553 *Agrobacterium* strains. (A) Relative root length (% of the initial root length at day 0) was
554 measured after 8 and 16 days of culture in four lines transformed by C58C1 and four lines
555 transformed by K599. Three independent biological replicates were performed, and the data are
556 presented as mean values with standard deviation. (B) Representative images of hairy root lines
557 at the initial time point and after 8 days of culture. Scale bar represents 1 mm.

558

559 **Supplementary Figure S3.** Promoter fragments of *BnaIAA* genes used in the BIP3 reporter
560 construct. AuxRE motifs in the forward orientation (TGTCCC) are indicated by green boxes,
561 whereas AuxRE motifs in the reverse orientation (GGGACA) are indicated by blue boxes.

562

563 **Supplementary Figure S4.** Histochemical GUS staining of different tissues of *B. napus*
564 transgenic plants. Independent transgenic lines from (A) DR5cc-GUS (+/- Ω) and (B) BIP3-
565 GUS (+/- Ω) are presented. Scale bars represent 2 mm (seedlings, flowers), 200 μ m (root tips),
566 and 500 μ m (embryos).

567

568 **Supplementary Figure S5.** Histochemical GUS staining of *B. napus* flowers expressing
569 DR5cc-GUS (+/- Ω) or BIP3-GUS (+/- Ω). Flowers were sprayed with water (Mock) or 50 μ M
570 NAA in water, and stained after 24 h. Scale bars represent 2 mm.

571

572 **Supplementary Figure S6.** The DR5cc reporter is auxin responsive in *B. napus* hairy roots.
573 **(A)** Maximum intensity projections of root tips from independent lines expressing DR5cc- Ω -
574 VENUS or DR5cc- Ω -mCherry treated with mock or 1 μ M NAA, and imaged after 6 or 24 h.
575 Scale bars represent 40 μ m. **(B)** Quantification of relative VENUS and mCherry fluorescence
576 intensities in mock- and NAA-treated hairy roots at indicated time points. Error bars indicate
577 SD (n = individual roots); **P < 0.01; ***P < 0.001; Dunnett's test. For each time point, values
578 are normalized to the corresponding mock.

579

580 **Supplementary Figure S7.** Stress-induced auxin signaling dynamics in hairy roots expressing
581 DR5cc- Ω -mCherry (Line 1). Maximum intensity projections of root tips treated with mock and
582 abiotic stress (150 mM mannitol or 75 mM NaCl), and imaged at 1, 6, 12, and 24 h. Scale bars
583 represent 40 μ m. Quantification is shown in Figure 4.

584

585 **Supplementary Figure S8.** Stress-induced auxin signaling dynamics in hairy roots expressing
586 DR5cc- Ω -VENUS (Line 2). **(A)** Maximum intensity projections of root tips treated with mock
587 and abiotic stress (150 mM mannitol or 75 mM NaCl), and imaged at 1, 6, 12, and 24 h. Scales
588 bars represent 40 μ m. **(B)** Quantification of relative VENUS fluorescence intensity in mock-
589 and stress-treated hairy roots at indicated time points. Error bars indicate SD (n = individual
590 roots); **P < 0.01; ***P < 0.001; Dunnett's test. For each time point, values are normalized to
591 the corresponding mock.

592

593 **Supplementary Figure S9.** Stress-induced auxin signaling dynamics in hairy roots expressing
594 DR5cc- Ω -mCherry (Line 2). **(A)** Maximum intensity projections of root tips treated with mock
595 and abiotic stress (150 mM mannitol or 75 mM NaCl), and imaged at 1, 6, 12, and 24 h. Scale
596 bars represent 40 μ m. **(B)** Quantification of relative mCherry fluorescence intensity in mock-
597 and stress-treated hairy roots at indicated time points. Error bars indicate SD (n = individual
598 roots); *P < 0.05; **P < 0.01; ***P < 0.001; Dunnett's test. For each time point, values are
599 normalized to the corresponding mock.

600

601

602 **Supplementary Figure S10.** Cytokinin and auxin reporter activity in *B. napus* hairy roots,
603 transgenic Line 2. **(A)** Maximum intensity projections of hairy roots co-expressing TCSv2-
604 VENUS and DR5-mCherry treated with mock, NAA (1 μ M, 24 h), and/or BAP (5 μ M, 2 h).
605 Images are shown as VENUS (top row), mCherry (middle row) and merged channels (bottom
606 row: magenta color for DR5cc- Ω -mCherry and yellow for TCSv2-VENUS). Scale bars
607 represent 20 μ m. **(B)** Quantification of relative VENUS (left) and mCherry (right) fluorescence
608 intensities in mock- and hormone-treated hairy roots. Error bars indicate SD (n = individual
609 roots); ***P < 0.001; Dunnett's test. For each channel, values are normalized to the
610 corresponding mock.

611

612 **Supplementary Figure S11.** *BnaIAA* genes selected for qDII reporter construction. The coding
613 regions of *BnaA01g24190D* (**A**; *IAA2*) and *BnaA08g27770D* (**B**; *IAA17*), together with their
614 corresponding amino acid sequences, are shown. KR motif is highlighted in green, the degron
615 motif in yellow, and the degron tail in blue.

616

617 **Supplementary Figure S12.** qDII reporters are auxin responsive in *B. napus* hairy roots. (**A**,
618 **B**) *IAA2* Line 2 and (**C**, **D**) *IAA17* Line 2 showing representative epidermal cell images under
619 mock and NAA (10 μ M, 2 h) conditions, with TagBFP (left) and VENUS (right) channels, and
620 corresponding VENUS/TagBFP fluorescence intensity quantifications. Values are normalized
621 to the corresponding mock. Scale bars represent 20 μ m. Error bars indicate SD (n = individual
622 roots); **P < 0.01; ***P < 0.001; Welch's t-test.

623

624 **Supplementary Figure S13.** Stability of the TagBFP fluorescence in qDII constructs.
625 Quantification of relative TagBFP fluorescence intensity in independent hairy root lines
626 expressing qDII-*IAA2* / *IAA17* treated with mock or NAA (10 μ M, 2 h). Error bars indicate
627 SD. No significant differences were observed in treated samples compared with the mock
628 control (Welch's t-test).

629

630 **Supplementary Figure S14.** Schematic representation of the constructs prepared for this study.
631 Addgene plasmids used for MoClo cloning are indicated.

632

633 **Supplementary Figure S15.** Sequence alignment of the two *ACC* gene copies in *B. napus*
634 DH12075. Amplification primers for the 0.6 kb fragment are highlighted in green, whereas
635 primers and probes specific for the *ACC-A* copy used in qPCR are highlighted in blue and
636 yellow, respectively.

637

638 **Supplementary Table S1.** List of oligonucleotides.

639

640 References

- 641 1 Li L, Gallei M, Friml J. Bending to auxin: fast acid growth for tropisms. *Trends Plant*
642 *Sci* 2022; **27**: 440–449.
- 643 2 Di Mambro R *et al.* Auxin minimum triggers the developmental switch from cell division
644 to cell differentiation in the *Arabidopsis* root. *Proceedings of the National Academy of*
645 *Sciences* 2017; **114**. doi:10.1073/pnas.1705833114.

- 646 3 Verma S, Attuluri VPS, Robert HS. An Essential Function for Auxin in Embryo
647 Development. *Cold Spring Harb Perspect Biol* 2021; **13**: a039966.
- 648 4 Simon S, Petrášek J. Why plants need more than one type of auxin. *Plant Science* 2011;
649 **180**: 454–460.
- 650 5 Yu Z, Zhang F, Friml J, Ding Z. Auxin signaling: Research advances over the past 30
651 years. *J Integr Plant Biol* 2022; **64**: 371–392.
- 652 6 Qi L *et al.* Adenylate cyclase activity of TIR1/AFB auxin receptors in plants. *Nature*
653 2022; **611**: 133–138.
- 654 7 Chen H *et al.* TIR1-produced cAMP as a second messenger in transcriptional auxin
655 signalling. *Nature* 2025; **640**: 1011–1016.
- 656 8 Jedličková V, Ebrahimi Naghani S, Robert HS. On the trail of auxin: Reporters and
657 sensors. *Plant Cell* 2022; **34**: 3200–3213.
- 658 9 Ulmasov T, Liu ZB, Hagen G, Guilfoyle TJ. Composite structure of auxin response
659 elements. *Plant Cell* 1995; **7**: 1611–1623.
- 660 10 Ulmasov T, Murfett J, Hagen G, Guilfoyle TJ. Aux/IAA proteins repress expression of
661 reporter genes containing natural and highly active synthetic auxin response elements.
662 *Plant Cell* 1997; **9**: 1963–1971.
- 663 11 Friml J *et al.* AtPIN4 Mediates Sink-driven auxin gradients and root patterning in
664 *Arabidopsis*. *Cell* 2002; **108**: 661–673.
- 665 12 Boer DR *et al.* Structural basis for DNA binding specificity by the auxin-dependent ARF
666 transcription factors. *Cell* 2014; **156**: 577–589.
- 667 13 Liao C-Y, Smet W, Brunoud G, Yoshida S, Vernoux T, Weijers D. Reporters for sensitive
668 and quantitative measurement of auxin response. *Nat Methods* 2015; **12**: 207–210.
- 669 14 Freire-Rios A *et al.* Architecture of DNA elements mediating ARF transcription factor
670 binding and auxin-responsive gene expression in *Arabidopsis*. *Proceedings of the*
671 *National Academy of Sciences* 2020; **117**: 24557–24566.
- 672 15 Lieberman-Lazarovich M, Yahav C, Israeli A, Efroni I. Deep conservation of cis-element
673 variants regulating plant hormonal responses. *Plant Cell* 2019; **31**: tpc.00129.2019.
- 674 16 Pacios-Bras C *et al.* Auxin distribution in *Lotus japonicus* during root nodule
675 development. *Plant Mol Biol* 2003; **52**: 1169–1180.
- 676 17 Li Y, Hagen G, Guilfoyle TJ. An Auxin-Responsive Promoter Is Differentially Induced
677 by Auxin Gradients during Tropisms. *Plant Cell* 1991; **3**: 1167–1175.
- 678 18 Hagen G, Martin G, Li Y, Guilfoyle TJ. Auxin-induced expression of the soybean GH3
679 promoter in transgenic tobacco plants. *Plant Mol Biol* 1991; **17**: 567–579.

- 680 19 Brunoud G *et al.* A novel sensor to map auxin response and distribution at high spatio-
681 temporal resolution. *Nature* 2012; **482**: 103–106.
- 682 20 Vernoux T *et al.* The auxin signalling network translates dynamic input into robust
683 patterning at the shoot apex. *Mol Syst Biol* 2011; **7**. doi:10.1038/msb.2011.39.
- 684 21 Galvan-Ampudia CS *et al.* Temporal integration of auxin information for the regulation
685 of patterning. *Elife* 2020; **9**. doi:10.7554/eLife.55832.
- 686 22 Figueiredo MRA de *et al.* An in-frame deletion mutation in the degron tail of auxin
687 coreceptor *IAA2* confers resistance to the herbicide 2,4-D in *Sisymbrium orientale*.
688 *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 2022; **119**.
689 doi:10.1073/pnas.2105819119.
- 690 23 Figueiredo MRA de, Strader LC. Intrinsic and extrinsic regulators of Aux/IAA protein
691 degradation dynamics. *Trends Biochem Sci* 2022; **47**: 865–874.
- 692 24 Winkler M *et al.* Variation in auxin sensing guides AUX/IAA transcriptional repressor
693 ubiquitylation and destruction. *Nat Commun* 2017; **8**: 15706.
- 694 25 Moss BL *et al.* Rate motifs tune Auxin/Indole-3-Acetic Acid degradation dynamics.
695 *Plant Physiol* 2015; **169**: 803–813.
- 696 26 Dreher KA, Brown J, Saw RE, Callis J. The *Arabidopsis* Aux/IAA protein family has
697 diversified in degradation and auxin responsiveness. *Plant Cell* 2006; **18**: 699–714.
- 698 27 Hernández M, Río A, Esteve T, Prat S, Pla M. A Rapeseed-specific gene, *Acetyl-CoA*
699 *Carboxylase*, can be used as a reference for qualitative and real-time quantitative PCR
700 detection of transgenes from mixed food samples. *J Agric Food Chem* 2001; **49**: 3622–
701 3627.
- 702 28 Long L *et al.* Establishment and validation of reference genes of *Brassica napus* L. for
703 digital PCR detection of genetically modified canola. *Foods* 2022; **11**: 2535.
- 704 29 Weng H, Pan A, Yang L, Zhang C, Liu Z, Zhang D. Estimating number of transgene
705 copies in transgenic rapeseed by real-time PCR assay with HMG I/Y as an endogenous
706 reference gene. *Plant Mol Biol Report* 2004; **22**: 289–300.
- 707 30 Jedličková V *et al.* Hairy root transformation system as a tool for CRISPR/Cas9-directed
708 genome editing in oilseed rape (*Brassica napus*). *Front Plant Sci* 2022; **13**: 919290.
- 709 31 Chao H *et al.* BrassicaEDB: a gene expression database for Brassica crops. *Int J Mol Sci*
710 2020; **21**: 5831.
- 711 32 Christey MC. Use of ri-mediated transformation for production of transgenic plants. *In*
712 *Vitro Cellular & Developmental Biology - Plant* 2001; **37**: 687–700.
- 713 33 Jing H, Wilkinson EG, Sageman-Furnas K, Strader LC. Auxin and abiotic stress
714 responses. *J Exp Bot* 2023; **74**: 7000–7014.

- 715 34 Nicolas Mala KL *et al.* Primary multistep phosphorelay activation comprises both
716 cytokinin and abiotic stress responses: insights from comparative analysis of *Brassica*
717 type-A response regulators. *J Exp Bot* 2024; **75**: 6346–6368.
- 718 35 Shrestha A *et al.* *Lotus japonicus* Nuclear Factor YAI, a nodule emergence stage-specific
719 regulator of auxin signalling. *New Phytologist* 2021; **229**: 1535–1552.
- 720 36 Flores-Moreno BA, Palomino-Juárez NF, Nanjareddy K, Arthikala M-K. A simplified
721 and rapid hairy root transformation system for functional promoter and symbiosis studies
722 in Fenugreek (*Trigonella foenum-graecum*). *Gene Rep* 2026; **43**: 102492.
- 723 37 Demina I V. *et al.* Accumulation of and response to auxins in roots and nodules of the
724 actinorhizal plant *Datisca glomerata* compared to the model legume *Medicago*
725 *truncatula*. *Front Plant Sci* 2019; **10**. doi:10.3389/fpls.2019.01085.
- 726 38 Shvets DYu, Berezhneva ZA, Musin KhG, Kuluev BR. Effect of *rol* genes of the A4,
727 15834, and K599 strains of *Agrobacterium rhizogenes* on root growth and states of the
728 antioxidant systems of transgenic Tobacco plants subjected to abiotic stress. *Russian*
729 *Journal of Plant Physiology* 2024; **71**: 165.
- 730 39 De Block M, Debrouwer D. Two T-DNA's co-transformed into *Brassica napus* by a
731 double *Agrobacterium tumefaciens* infection are mainly integrated at the same locus.
732 *Theoretical and Applied Genetics* 1991; **82**: 257–263.
- 733 40 Komari T, Hiei Y, Saito Y, Murai N, Kumashiro T. Vectors carrying two separate T-DNAs
734 for co-transformation of higher plants mediated by *Agrobacterium tumefaciens* and
735 segregation of transformants free from selection markers. *The Plant Journal* 1996; **10**:
736 165–174.
- 737 41 Al Nuaimi M, Rafi M, ElSiddig M, Aldarmaki M, George S, Amiri KMA. T-DNA
738 orientation, distance between two T-DNAs, and the transformation target cells
739 significantly impact vector backbone integration and efficiency of generating marker-
740 free transgenic plants in a co-transformation system. *The Plant Journal* 2025; **124**.
741 doi:10.1111/tpj.70510.
- 742 42 De Buck S, Podevin N, Nolf J, Jacobs A, Depicker A. The T-DNA integration pattern in
743 *Arabidopsis* transformants is highly determined by the transformed target cell. *The Plant*
744 *Journal* 2009; **60**: 134–145.
- 745 43 Smolko A, Bauer N, Pavlović I, Pěňčík A, Novák O, Salopek-Sondi B. Altered root
746 growth, auxin metabolism and distribution in *Arabidopsis thaliana* exposed to salt and
747 osmotic stress. *Int J Mol Sci* 2021; **22**: 7993.
- 748 44 Aloni R, Aloni E, Langhans M, Ullrich CI. Role of auxin in regulating *Arabidopsis*
749 flower development. *Planta* 2006; **223**: 315–328.
- 750 45 Maurel C, Barbier-Brygoo H, Spena A, Tempé J, Guern J. Single *rol* genes from the
751 *Agrobacterium rhizogenes* T_L-DNA alter some of the cellular responses to auxin in
752 *Nicotiana tabacum*. *Plant Physiol* 1991; **97**: 212–216.

- 753 46 Mauro ML, Costantino P, Bettini PP. The never-ending story of *rol* genes: a century after.
754 *Plant Cell, Tissue and Organ Culture (PCTOC)* 2017; **131**: 201–212.
- 755 47 Isoda R *et al.* Sensors for the quantification, localization and analysis of the dynamics of
756 plant hormones. *The Plant Journal* 2021; **105**: 542–557.
- 757 48 Robil JM, McSteen P. Hormonal control of medial–lateral growth and vein formation in
758 the maize leaf. *New Phytologist* 2023; **238**: 125–141.
- 759 49 Yang J *et al.* Dynamic regulation of auxin response during rice development revealed by
760 newly established hormone biosensor markers. *Front Plant Sci* 2017; **8**.
761 doi:10.3389/fpls.2017.00256.
- 762 50 Steiner E *et al.* Characterization of the cytokinin sensor TCSv2 in *Arabidopsis* and
763 tomato. *Plant Methods* 2020; **16**: 152.
- 764 51 Galvan-Ampudia CS *et al.* Halotropism is a response of plant roots to avoid a saline
765 environment. *Current Biology* 2013; **23**: 2044–2050.
- 766 52 Vanneste S, Pei Y, Friml J. Mechanisms of auxin action in plant growth and development.
767 *Nat Rev Mol Cell Biol* 2025; **26**: 648–666.
- 768 53 Weber E, Engler C, Gruetzner R, Werner S, Marillonnet S. A modular cloning system for
769 standardized assembly of multigene constructs. *PLoS One* 2011; **6**: e16765.
- 770 54 Engler C *et al.* A Golden Gate modular cloning toolbox for plants. *ACS Synth Biol* 2014;
771 **3**: 839–843.
- 772 55 Li J-F *et al.* Multiplex and homologous recombination–mediated genome editing in
773 *Arabidopsis* and *Nicotiana benthamiana* using guide RNA and Cas9. *Nat Biotechnol*
774 2013; **31**: 688–691.
- 775 56 Gantner J *et al.* Peripheral infrastructure vectors and an extended set of plant parts for
776 the Modular Cloning system. *PLoS One* 2018; **13**: e0197185.
- 777 57 Li H, Wang B, Zhang Q, Wang J, King GJ, Liu K. Genome-wide analysis of the
778 auxin/indoleacetic acid (Aux/IAA) gene family in allotetraploid rapeseed (*Brassica*
779 *napus* L.). *BMC Plant Biol* 2017; **17**: 204.
- 780 58 Petit A *et al.* Further extension of the opine concept: plasmids in *Agrobacterium*
781 *rhizogenes* cooperate for opine degradation. *Mol Gen Genet* 1983; **190**: 204–214.
- 782 59 Jedličková V, Štefková M, Sedláček M, Panzarová K, Robert HS. Hairy root
783 transformation and regeneration in *Arabidopsis thaliana* and *Brassica napus*. *Journal of*
784 *Visualized Experiments* 2023; **202**: e66223.
- 785 60 Allen GC, Flores-Vergara MA, Krasynanski S, Kumar S, Thompson WF. A modified
786 protocol for rapid DNA isolation from plant tissues using cetyltrimethylammonium
787 bromide. *Nat Protoc* 2006; **1**: 2320–2325.

788 61 Schneider CA, Rasband WS, Eliceiri KW. NIH Image to ImageJ: 25 years of image
789 analysis. *Nat Methods* 2012; **9**: 671–675.
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AuxRE TGTCCC

B

